

The Influence of Cryptocurrency Transaction as a Currency in NFT-Based Game Transactions

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Abstract — Cryptocurrency is a digital or virtual currency that is guaranteed by cryptography along with the emergence of cryptocurrency, the emergence of NFT is also widely discussed, NFT is referred to as a digital asset in the form of works of art or collectibles such as photos, pictures, videos, games and so on. Currently, cryptocurrency-based NFT games are being discussed as a transaction method, with the emergence of this transaction method reaping many pros and cons. To be able to find out the acceptance and use of Cryptocurrency methods in this NFT game. UTAUT is used as a research model UTAUT is a model to explain user behavior toward information technology. UTAUT is formulated with 4 core determinants of intention and usage, namely performance expectancy, effort expectancy, social influence, & facilitating conditions. This study used a questionnaire for sampling and obtained 244 respondents who had used the cryptocurrency transaction method in this NFT game. This study aims to prove the effect of independent variables (Performance Expectations, Effort Expectations, Social Influence, Perceived Risk, Trust, Facilitation Conditions) on the dependent variable (Behavioral Intentions and Usage Behavior). The results showed that there were positive and negative effects. Performance Expectations, Effort Expectations, Social Influences, Risks, and Facilitation Conditions have a positive and significant impact on Behavioral Intentions. Meanwhile, the Trust variable does not effect on Behavioral intentions, and Behavioral intentions have a positive effect on user behavior

Keywords— Cryptocurrency, NFT, UTAUT, game, SmartPLS

I. INTRODUCTION

Currently, cryptocurrency digital currency is being discussed, due to the large number of world technology companies creating new innovations in this Cryptocurrency.

Coupled with the world giant Facebook which changed its name to Meta and several large companies that created games that used cryptocurrency and NFTs as currency on the game. This cryptocurrency has created many nouveau riche people. As was the case in February 2021, a man from Los Angeles, US, bought 5 million Dogecoin from all his savings worth US\$ 188 thousand million or IDR 2.73 billion, and his savings funds became US\$ 1.88 million or IDR 27.26 billion (Browne, 2021)

The phenomenon of digital currency Cryptocurrency, which creates a lot of nouveau riche people. So that there are so many people who are interested in entering cryptocurrency to be used as an investment tool or as a means of transaction. Cryptocurrency is a virtual currency based on blockchain used as a transaction tool, where the currency is generated and can be traded through cryptographic processes.

At first, the use of Cryptocurrencies first appeared in the 1980s, David Chaum invented a special algorithm that later became the virtual currency of today. Bitcoin is the first cryptocurrency, Satoshi Nakamoto the owner of bitcoin describes the cryptocurrency asset project, which is an electronic payment system based on verified cryptographic evidence and recorded in the blockchain system

With this cryptocurrency, it is considered that it will facilitate transactions because it can be done globally. Currently, millennials and gen z generations use Cryptocurrency as an investment instrument (Sun, Dedahanov, Shin, & Kim). Indonesia is currently still in the earliest stages of adopting Cryptocurrencies and NFTs. For this reason, more education is needed so that the public better understands the use of this technology to avoid irresponsible projects and currently Indonesia is one of the largest investors (Ferdig, Cohen, Ling, & Hartshorne, 2022)

Figure 1 When did you first hear of Crypto Assets (Tennant, 2021)

According to figure 1, *Cryptocurrency* enthusiasts in Indonesia increased from year to year, which previously from 2015 to 2016 the table of stable crypto enthusiasts did not increase, and then 2017 to 2018 experienced an increase, and a very significant increase, namely in 2021

Figure 2 Crypto Spread In Developed and Developing Countries (Redman, 2020)

Viewed in figure 2. There are several experiments conducted in several countries by attracting some respondents to see if Cryptocurrency assets are recognized and to see the rate of spread of Cryptocurrencies that exist in those countries by giving each country 10 coins each and distributed to individuals. And in this experiment, Indonesia with 100 participants was able to attract 4,350 people so that Indonesia became number 1 with the largest spread beating the US, it is believed that developing countries have a greater rate of spread because small amounts of money are more valued in developing countries (Sakovich, 2020)

And for NFTs (Non-Fungible Tokens) it is almost the same as Cryptocurrencies because NFTs are Crypto derivative investments. NFTs are digital assets in the form of works of art, photos, images, audio recordings, videos, games, and others. What distinguishes Cryptocurrencies from NFTs is that crypto tokens have a fixed price according to the market, while the NFT token of each asset has a different price. NFTs can have a very high value depending on the value of the NFT itself. As in the case of 2021, The Merge NFT sold 91.8 million USD or worth 1.31 Trillion NFT owners The Merge is known to be able to create iconic works and is known as a digital artist Pak (Block, 2021)

With the emergence of NFT games with the P2E concept, it has greatly changed people's views on games that were previously games only for consumption but with the emergence of P2E, playing games has become something that makes money, in addition to being an income suggestion, P2E games can also be a means of investment (Magas, 2021). The game can be played via smartphones and computers. Play-To-Earn (P2E) games are known as GameFi where the game is a combination of gaming and decentralized finance (DeFi) (Feign & Leech, 2022)

The development of the Play-To-Earn game market is considered to continue to grow and there will be more and more fans because this P2E game does not have a centralized authority to control the game ecosystem. And because it uses blockchain-based technology that underlies this Play-To-Earn game, it allows players to make transactions without service fees so that players can buy and sell their assets. The presence of this game has created a new market trend in the market Noted in July 2021, more than 800 thousand active users in the Play-To-Earn game. It is recorded that this number has increased by 121% from the previous month, with the presence of this P2E game expected to be able to create a large market in the next few years. In one of the *Cryptocurrency* marketplaces, Coinmarketcap recorded sales of *NFT* assets in the crypto market of \$2.5 billion throughout 2021. With this value, it is considered that it will continue to increase along with the trend of *NFT* games that continue to emerge.

Figure 3 Gamers are embracing NFT Through Playing Video Game (Interpret, 2022)

According to figure 3, it is recorded that 57% of the 1,500 respondents are interested in getting *NFTs* from video games, and more than 43% indicate that their interest in playing this *NFT* game is to generate *NFTs* and that is the main driver for them to play. This *NFT* game provides a greater sense of ownership of the items they get both in the game and outside (Interpret, 2022) Therefore, with the existence of *NFT* games that adopt *Cryptocurrency* as a transaction tool in this study, they will conduct a search related to what factors cause people to want to play this *NFT* game and make transactions in this *NFT* game. There are 8 variables that will be studied in this study, Performance using Unified Theory and Acceptance and Use of The Technology (UTAUT). Of the 8 existing variables, there are 2 different variables, namely Facilitating Conditions to *Use behavior*, in previous research related to Facilitating Conditions, the fundamental drivers for adopting technology, facilitating conditions have a positive and significant effect on the intention to adopt cryptocurrencies (Abbasi, Tiew, Tang, Goh, & Thurasamy, 2021).

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 Cryptocurrencies

Cryptocurrency is now an alternative currency for making transactions and for investing like a bank. *Cryptocurrency* assets can be traded and can be used as an investment tool. Some countries have made *Cryptocurrency* of the Bitcoin type as a currency that can be used as a legal transaction tool, namely El Salvador.

The use of this *Cryptocurrency* in some countries has increased due to the pandemic, in February 2020. Nigeria dominates the position with 34 percent as the owner of the most crypto.

Based on research conducted (Mokni, Bouteska, & Nakhli, 2022) During the COVID-19 pandemic, *Cryptocurrencies* of the Bitcoin type experienced a sharp increase. This increase in Bitcoin will have a positive effect on other types of coins. In recent years we have been hit with a major outbreak, namely COVID-19, at the time of this pandemic, *Cryptocurrency* users have increased. During this pandemic, people allocate their funds to invest in *Cryptocurrencies* because they are considered to have a high value (Iqbal, Fareed, Wan, & Shahzad, 2021). So with the increasing level of *cryptocurrency* popularity, *NFT* games were created that use *Cryptocurrency* as a currency for transactions.

2.2 NFT

NFT digital assets in 2021 have attracted the attention of the public as they have experienced record sales. In 2021 in Indonesia since the emergence of the Ghazali Effect, the *NFT* trend has been increasingly looked at by the public as an alternative to a investment. With the development of the *NFT* trend, well-known technology companies want to expand the development of the game industry's horizons by developing *NFT* games with *cryptocurrency* as their currency.

Based on existing research, *NFT* Games are different from just storing a collection of crypto coins in our wallets. *NFT* games have their mechanics, *NFT* games can represent unique characters or avatars as *NFTs*, the digital items you get from playing are also called *NFTs*. The amount of money that can be earned from this *NFT* game can be determined according to the goods, mechanisms, and market demands. (Binance, 2021)

2.3 UTAUT (Unified Theory of Acceptance and Use of Technology)

In the UTAUT model, four variables are a considerable determining factor for acceptance behavior (*behavioral intention*) and science and technology (*Use behavior*). The four determinant variables include performance expectations (*Performance expectancy*) is a person's idea that a system will help individuals in meeting their work performance goals (Lee & Shin, 2018). The second is business expectations (*Effort expectancy*) is a variable to assess the ease of using technology.

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The third is *social influence* which measures the level of an individual's perception of how much people around the individual believe in the significance of the use of technology (Setterstrom & Pearson, 2019), and the last is the facilitating conditions which refer to the extent to which the individual believes that the existing infrastructure within the organization is supportive in the use of technology (Moti & Walia, 2019). UTAUT can be a useful research model for research to assess the success rate of introducing new technologies to society. UTAUT unites the best characteristics derived from eight theories of technological acceptance so that the model is suitable for use in knowing the acceptance of new technologies (Williams, Rana, & Dwivedi, 2015) In this study, researchers used 8 variables contained in UTAUT, namely *performance expectancy*, *effort expectancy*, *social influence*, *trust*, *risk*, *facilitating conditions*, *behavioral intention*, *use behavioral* (Venkatesh, Thong, & Xu, 2012).

2.4 Effect of performance expectancy on behavioral intention

The use of *Performance expectancy* is intended to measure a person's level of *trust* in the use of technology can help him achieve advantages in the use of the system (Chin, Harris, & Brookshire, 2022). Someone believes that using a system can help and can get significant benefits in doing a job to increase interest in the use of information technology. The *behavioral intention* factor can be a reference to how much a person wants to use technology consistently. So the greater a person's intention to adopt technology continuously, it will make one believe that using the technology can provide benefits and provide benefits. *Performance expectancy* has a significant and positive effect on *behavioral intention*. Users of the *NFT* game-based Crypto transaction system provide benefits for users who have the intention to use this system constantly.

H1: Performance expectancy has a positive impact on Behavioral intention

2.5 Effect of effort expectancy on behavioral intention

Effort expectancy refers to the effort required in using a system, which determines whether the system is simple or complicated to use. *Cryptocurrency* has become an important part of *NFT* games because most *NFT* games use a decentralized system as the currency in the game. *Effort expectancy* is used to find out a person's comfort level in adopting this technology requires a lower effort.

Behavioral intention can be a reference in this study where if the user considers using this system free in a complicated effort, it can be ascertained that the user has the intention to adopt this system continuously. With the level of ease of use of the system on a system, it will cause a feeling in the user that using the system has benefits so that it makes users feel comfortable in using the system. *Effort expectancy* has a significant and positive effect on *behavioral intention*. Users of the transaction system.

H2: Effort expectancy positively affects Behavioral intention

2.6 Influence of social influence on behavioral intention

Social influence provides *social influence* on individuals and groups in using new technologies. This *social influence* factor is very important because most of the users do not have enough experience regarding new technologies, especially *NFT* games that implement cryptocurrencies, which is something that has been discussed lately. Which is adopted so that the influence of *social influence* has a great impact on a person's decision to make transactions. *Social influence* is one of the factors that determine *behavioral intention* towards the use of this transaction method, if a person's social environment uses the system a lot then the person will have more of a sense of waiting to use the system as well. *Social influence* has a significant and positive effect on *behavioral intention*.

H3: Social influence has a positive effect on Behavioral intention

2.7 The effect of perceived risk on behavioral intention

Perceived Risk is important in developing a new technology because every technology definitely has *risks*. The *risks* referred to in this study want to measure the level of *risk* that the technology has can have an impact on transactions from an individual. The use of *cryptocurrency* transactions has a fairly high level of *risk* because it all depends on the system, so that if the system has weaknesses, the *risk* received will be greater and if the system is strong, the *risk* received by users is lower. If the *risk* received by the user is low, the user will continue to use this transaction system because it is considered safe. So *trust* has a positive influence on *behavioral intentions*.

H4 : Risk of positive impact on Behavioral intention

2.8 The effect of trust on behavioral intention

Trust is the level of *trust* an individual feels safe in making a transaction using the transaction system.

Trust is an important factor in this study because using this game-based *cryptocurrency* transaction system, users rely on the system to process these transactions, so the higher the level of user *trust* in using this transaction system, the user will continue to use this transaction system. *Trusts* are vulnerable because it is difficult to gain *trust* when the user experience is not very good. Thus, *trust* has a strong influence on *behavioral intentions*

H5 : *Trust has a positive effect on Behavioral intention*

2.9 Effect of facilitating conditions on behavioral intention

Facilitating Conditions is an important thing in the research of this crypto-based transaction method, facilitating conditions themselves are variables that explain the objective factors that are supporting factors to facilitate the use of this transaction system (Correa, Cataluña, Gaitán, & Velicia, 2019). The use of a *cryptocurrency* transaction system requires good supporting facilities, with the facilitating conditions that support it, someone will have the intention to use a crypto-based transaction system. If the conditions are not supportive then someone will feel uncomfortable and the intention will decrease to use this crypto-based transaction system. So that facilitating conditions have a positive effect on *behavioral intention*.

H6: *Facilitating Conditions have a positive effect on Behavioral intention*

2.10 Effect of facilitating conditions on use behavior

The use of facilitating conditions in this study is to determine a person's *trust* in using this crypto-based transaction system. The use of the new system certainly does not escape the supporting facilities, with the facilitating conditions that support it, user behavior will continue to use this crypto-based transaction system, and if the facilitating conditions are not supportive, user behavior will choose to use other transaction systems. Then the need for good supporting facilities to make someone feel comfortable in using this transaction system. So that facilitating conditions have a positive effect on *use behavior*

H7: *Facilitating Conditions have a positive effect on Behavioral intention*

2.11 Effect of facilitating conditions on use behavior

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The use of the new system certainly does not escape the supporting facilities, with the facilitating conditions that support it, user behavior will continue to use this crypto-based transaction system, and if the facilitating conditions are not supportive, user behavior will choose to use other transaction systems. Then the need for good supporting facilities to make someone feel comfortable in using this transaction system. So that facilitating conditions have a positive effect on *use behavior*

H7: *Facilitating Conditions have a positive effect on Behavioral intention*

III. METHODOLOGY

3.1 Model Formation

This research adopts a model based on UTAUT theory as a research model because UTAUT is a model that explains user behavior towards information technology. Researchers used variables *performance expectancy* (PE), *effort expectancy* (EE), *social influence* (SI), *perceived risk* (PR), *trust* (TT), *social influence* (SI), *facilitating conditions* (FC), *behavioral intention* (BI), *use behavior* (UB) On each variable determined by the researcher has a solid basis. The *Cryptocurrency* transaction method in this *NFT* game is a new thing, so an approach is needed to find out what factors make people who play *NFT* games want to use *cryptocurrency* as their transaction method, namely with the six variables that have a role to influence BI and UB

3.2 Types and sources of data

In this study, the researcher used a quantitative data approach and the data source in this study was primary data. Quantitative data is data that contains data in the form of information or explanations that can be calculated directly. The use of this type of data can be processed with statistical techniques and obtained using data collection techniques by applying answers in the form of scores. The main purpose of this study is to collect data to be processed and obtain data for the results of the study, researchers use primary quantitative data where the researcher will determine the subject as well as samples and populations.

3.3 Population

In this study, researchers used the slovin formula to determine the number of samples to be searched, researchers have a target population of PC gamers in Indonesia.

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The total population of gamers in Indonesia is 24,990,000 people and in this study researchers used a margin of error of 5%, and in this calculation got the results of 400 samples to be searched

$$n = \frac{N}{1 + Ne^2}$$

Figure 4 Slovin Formula

Information:

n = Sample Size,

N = Population Size

E = Margin of error

3.4 Data collection techniques

In this study using primary data techniques, the research will distribute questionnaires online using Google Form as a medium, this questionnaire will be distributed through social media, instant messaging applications, and other people who want to be involved in filling out this research. In this questionnaire, researchers used a one-six Likert scale, namely one (strongly disagree), two (disagree), three (disagree enough), four (agree enough), five (agree), and six (strongly agree) with the six-point scale to avoid neutral answers from respondents. It will take one week from June 27, 2022 to July 3, 2022, and this questionnaire is focused on those who use cryptocurrencies as a transaction tool in *NFT* games. In this study, researchers needed 250 respondents to get the results of the study to be processed. Researchers use primary data collection techniques, this primary data collection technique is the most strategic step in conducting this study, because the main purpose of this study is to collect data for processing.

3.5 Research Methods

This research method uses a quantitative research model with the distribution of questionnaires with the help of Microsoft Excel spreadsheets and SmartPLS software and this research model uses the UTAUT model.

Using this quantitative research we can assess and measure the possibilities that will occur in the application of new technologies. UTAUT combines several theories of acceptance of new technologies to be more accurate than the previous ones. The theories of eight theories in question are the Theory of Reasoned Action (TRA), Technology Acceptance Model (TAM), Motivational Model (MM), Theory of Planned Behavior (TPB), Combined TAM and TPB, Model of PC Utilization (MPCU), Innovation Diffusion Theory (IDT), and Social Cognitive Theory (SCT) After evaluating the eight existing models, researchers used six determinants, namely *Performance expectancy*, *effort expectancy*, *social influence*, *perceived risk*, *trust*, *facilitating conditions* which are the main roles as direct determinants of *behavioral intention* and *use behavior*

Figure 5 Research Model

3.6 Indicator and Variable

In this study, researchers used questionnaires as a data collection tool from this study. This questionnaire is prepared based on the variables contained in the model that researchers use, namely UTAUT (Unified Theory of Acceptance and Use of Technology). As well as on each variable is given an indicator that aims to find out what statement will be discussed. The questionnaire of this study contained 24 statements and used a 6-level likert scale.

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Table 1
Indicator and Variable

Variable	Indicator	Statement	Literature
<i>Performance expectancy</i>	Perceived Usefulness	Cryptocurrencies are very useful for me in facilitating buying and selling transactions on <i>NFT</i> games	(Meier, Mattke, & Maier, 2022)
	Job-fit	I believe that when using <i>cryptocurrency</i> as a transaction method will improve performance inside <i>NFT</i> games	(Meier, Mattke, & Maier, 2022)
	Relative advantage	By using <i>cryptocurrency</i> as a transaction method in <i>NFT</i> games I believe that this is a good innovation	(Meier, Mattke, & Maier, 2022)
	Outcome Expectation	I believe that the existence of this <i>cryptocurrency</i> transaction method in <i>NFT</i> games can improve the transaction system in other games	(Meier, Mattke, & Maier, 2022)
<i>Effort expectancy</i>	Easy To Learn	I easily learned in using <i>cryptocurrency</i> as a transaction method in <i>NFT</i> games	(Meier, Mattke, & Maier, 2022)
		I can easily be skilled in using <i>cryptocurrency</i> transaction methods on <i>NFT</i> games	(Meier, Mattke, & Maier, 2022)
	Ease of use	The explanation of the use of cryptocurrencies in <i>NFT</i> games is very easy to understand	(Meier, Mattke, & Maier, 2022)
<i>Social influence</i>	Subjective norms	I used the <i>cryptocurrency</i> transaction method on this <i>NFT</i> game because of a recommendation from a friend of mine	(Meier, Mattke, & Maier, 2022)
<i>Trust</i>	<i>Trustworth</i>	I am sure that this	(Oliveira

	y	method of <i>cryptocurrency</i> transactions can be trusted	, Faria, Thomas, & Popovic [~] , 2014)
	<i>Trust</i>	I believe in the <i>cryptocurrency</i> transaction method on this <i>NFT</i> game	(Oliveira, Faria, Thomas, & Popovic [~] , 2014)
	Assurance	When using this <i>cryptocurrency</i> transaction method I feel good security	(Oliveira, Faria, Thomas, & Popovic [~] , 2014)
<i>Risk</i>	Security Risk	I am not sure that using this <i>cryptocurrency</i> transaction method is safe	(Slade, Dwivedi, Piercy, & Williams, 2015)
		I am concerned about my personal data when using this transaction method	(Slade, Dwivedi, Piercy, & Williams, 2015)
	Financial Risk	I am afraid of losing money when using <i>cryptocurrency</i> transaction methods on <i>NFT</i> games	(Slade, Dwivedi, Piercy, & Williams, 2015)
	Operasional Risk	I do not believe in the operating system of this <i>cryptocurrency</i> transaction method	(Slade, Dwivedi, Piercy, & Williams, 2015)
<i>Facilitating Conditions</i>	Perceived Behavioral Control	I am sure of the system used to carry out transaction activities in <i>NFT</i> games well	(Slade, Dwivedi, Piercy, & Williams, 2015)
		I am sure that the system will be able to support the use of <i>cryptocurrency</i> transaction systems in <i>NFT</i> games	(Slade, Dwivedi, Piercy, & Williams, 2015)
	Resource	I have a device that	(Slade,

		supports playing <i>NFT</i> games and making transactions with cryptocurrencies	Dwivedi, Piercy, & Williams, 2015)
	Help	I was able to get help from others when I was having difficulty in using the <i>cryptocurrency</i> transaction method on this <i>NFT</i> game	(Slade, Dwivedi, Piercy, & Williams, 2015)
<i>Behavioral intention</i>	Repurchase Intention	I will use the <i>cryptocurrency</i> transaction method on the <i>NFT</i> game continuously	(Thomas, Singh, & Gaffar, 2013)
	Try To Use	I will always try to use the <i>cryptocurrency</i> transaction method in <i>NFT</i> games	(Thomas, Singh, & Gaffar, 2013)
<i>Use behavior</i>	Depth of Use	Every day I always use the <i>cryptocurrency</i> transaction method on <i>NFT</i> games	(Thomas, Singh, & Gaffar, 2013)
	Satisfaction	I am satisfied to use the <i>cryptocurrency</i> transaction method on this <i>NFT</i> game	(Thomas, Singh, & Gaffar, 2013)

Figure 6 Path Diagram

4.2 Demographics of Respondents Based on how often to make transactions using cryptocurrencies on *NFT* games

Figure 7 Demographics of Respondents Based on how often to make transactions using cryptocurrencies in *NFT* games

Figure 7 shows the results of research data from an online questionnaire based on how often to make transactions using cryptocurrencies on *NFT* games which are divided into 3 categories, namely < 5 times, <10 times, <20 times.

IV. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

4.1 Diagram Path Creation

The first step taken by the researcher is to make a path diagram based on the model used by the researcher in this study. There are six independent variables and two dependent variables in this study. Exogenous variables in this model are *performance expectancy* (PE), *effort expectancy* (EE), *social influence* (SI), *facilitating conditions* (FC), *perceived risk* (PR), and *trust* (TR). And for the dependent variables in this model are *behavioral intention* (BI) and *use behavior* (UB) And for the figure of the path diagram can be seen in the following figure.

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It can be known from the 244 respondents that researchers obtained, there were 49.2% <5 in 1 month, 30.7% <10 in 1 month, and <20 in 1 month. So what dominates this data is that < 5 times in 1 month.

4.3 Reliability Testing On Cronbach's Alpha

Reliability testing is carried out with the aim of showing the level of reliability of the indicators used, a good reliability test is if each indicator has a value above 0.7 (Heale & Twycross, 2015). In testing this reliability, the tester calculated using SmartPLS software. Cronbach's Alpha is commonly used to measure the reliability of the indicators used in research questionnaires. The results of the reliability test with the Cronbach's Alpha test can be seen in the following table. Based on the results of the reliability test, it can be seen that all statements on independent and dependent variables have values above 0.7 so that they can be inferred for all reliable questions

Table 2
Cronchach's alpha reliability results

Variable	Cronbach's Alpha
<i>Performance expectancy</i>	0.910
<i>Effort expectancy</i>	0.873
<i>Social influence</i>	1.000
<i>Perceived Risk</i>	0.839
<i>Trust</i>	0.885
<i>Facilitating Conditions</i>	0.765
<i>Behavioral intention</i>	0.857
<i>Use behavior</i>	0.862

4.4 Testing Reliability on Internal Consistency

Internal Consistency is a form of reliability used to assess the reliability of a good composite based on a composite reliability score. For composite reliability equal to cronbach alpha must have a value above 0.7 for a good reliability test. From table 3, it can be seen that the composite reliability value in all existing questions has a value above 0.7 so that it can be concluded for all reliable questions

Table 3
Composite reliability results

Variable	Composite Reliability
<i>Performance expectancy</i>	0.936
<i>Effort expectancy</i>	0.920
<i>Social influence</i>	1.000
<i>Perceived Risk</i>	0.902
<i>Trust</i>	0.920
<i>Facilitating Conditions</i>	0.849
<i>Behavioral intention</i>	0.931
<i>Use behavior</i>	0.935

4.5 Convergent Validity Testing

In the convergent validity test, it can be done if the Outer Loading value is above 0.7 then the convergent validity has been met

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Table 4
Outer loading results

Variable	Indicator	Outer Loading
<i>Performance expectancy</i>	PE1	0.884
	PE2	0.912
	PE3	0.881
	PE4	0.869
<i>Effort expectancy</i>	EE1	0.901
	EE2	0.963
	EE3	0.802
<i>Social influence</i>	SI1	1.000
<i>Perceived Risk</i>	PR1	0.820
	PR2	0.849
	PR3	0.901
	PR4	0.876
<i>Trust</i>	TR1	0.863
	TR2	0.926
	TR3	0.812
<i>Facilitating Conditions</i>	FC1	0.704
	FC2	0.772
	FC3	0.718
	FC4	0.857
<i>Behavioral intention</i>	BI1	0.908
	BI2	0.958
<i>Use behavior</i>	UB1	0.926
	UB2	0.948

From the table above, the value of the outer loading above has exceeded the specified value of 0.7. So the next step in testing the validity of this convergence is to look for the AVE (Average Variance Extracted) value, to find this AVE value, a result of more than 0.5 is needed to be declared valid, and if it is below that it will be declared invalid.

Table 5
AVE (Ave Variance Extracted) results

Variable	AVE (Average Variance Extracted)
<i>Performance expectancy</i>	0.786
<i>Effort expectancy</i>	0.794
<i>Social influence</i>	1.000
<i>Perceived Risk</i>	0.743
<i>Trust</i>	0.754
<i>Facilitating Conditions</i>	0.586
<i>Behavioral intention</i>	0.871
<i>Use behavior</i>	0.878

Testing the validity of the test using the ave result criteria (average variance extract) based on the results obtained in table 5 the results obtained from ave supporting conditions are the lowest compared to others.

4.6 Discriminant Validity Testing

Table 6
Crossloadings

	Behavioral In...	Effort Expe...	Facilitating ...	Perceived R...	Performanc...	Social Infru...	Trust	Use Behavior
BI1	0.908	0.442	0.616	0.484	0.603	0.438	0.540	0.432
BI2	0.958	0.629	0.833	0.618	0.758	0.534	0.787	0.741
EE1	0.516	0.901	0.370	0.621	0.141	0.065	0.596	0.478
EE2	0.659	0.963	0.628	0.689	0.437	0.121	0.771	0.773
EE3	0.300	0.802	0.542	0.656	0.369	0.205	0.661	0.837
FC1	0.466	0.270	0.704	0.261	0.468	0.129	0.536	0.385
FC2	0.653	0.500	0.772	0.497	0.644	0.298	0.710	0.606
FC3	0.576	0.481	0.718	0.549	0.657	0.560	0.534	0.694
FC4	0.696	0.456	0.857	0.553	0.704	0.569	0.645	0.686
PE1	0.577	0.201	0.631	0.415	0.884	0.615	0.563	0.519
PE2	0.768	0.422	0.808	0.570	0.912	0.530	0.665	0.762
PE3	0.580	0.265	0.729	0.438	0.881	0.646	0.577	0.621
PE4	0.689	0.323	0.726	0.381	0.869	0.453	0.585	0.523
PR1	0.431	0.474	0.498	0.820	0.438	0.629	0.367	0.486
PR2	0.487	0.581	0.607	0.849	0.492	0.493	0.651	0.643
PR3	0.524	0.675	0.589	0.901	0.542	0.452	0.624	0.787
PR4	0.604	0.730	0.489	0.876	0.327	0.328	0.528	0.647
SI1	0.528	0.130	0.541	0.535	0.624	1.000	0.353	0.430
TR1	0.753	0.644	0.725	0.522	0.619	0.361	0.863	0.630
TR2	0.574	0.666	0.765	0.587	0.612	0.312	0.926	0.868
TR3	0.534	0.665	0.563	0.550	0.519	0.222	0.812	0.740
UB1	0.938	0.777	0.681	0.807	0.503	0.420	0.805	0.926
UB2	0.681	0.644	0.803	0.616	0.773	0.389	0.786	0.948

Testing the Validity of discriminants using the crossloadings criterion looks for the value of the measured block of latent variables to be greater than other latent variables based on the table above, the EE3 indicator has a lower loading value than the *use behavior* variable, and for other indicators it is greater than other variables.

4.7 Normality Testing

Table 7
T Statistics

	Original Sa...	Sample Me...	Standard D...	T Statistics (L...	P Values
Behavioral Intention -> Use Behavior	0.065	0.055	0.055	1.189	0.235
Effort Expectancy -> Behavioral Intention	0.337	0.354	0.095	3.534	0.000
Facilitating Conditions -> Behavioral Intention	0.273	0.272	0.089	3.071	0.002
Facilitating Conditions -> Use Behavior	0.745	0.752	0.052	14.235	0.000
Perceived Risk -> Behavioral Intention	-0.104	-0.105	0.088	1.180	0.238
Performance Expectancy -> Behavioral Intention	0.310	0.327	0.068	4.576	0.000
Social Influence -> Behavioral Intention	0.180	0.175	0.072	2.511	0.012
Trust -> Behavioral Intention	0.051	0.030	0.115	0.444	0.657

Data from table 7, shows the results of data on T statistics, *behavioral intention* towards normally distributed *use behavior*, *effort expectancy* towards normal distributed *behavioral intention*, *facilitating conditions* to normal distributed *behavioral intention*, *facilitating conditions* to normal distributed *use behavior*, *perceived risk* to normally distributed *behavioral intention*, *performance expectancy* towards normal distributed *behavioral intention*, *social influence* on normal distributed *behavioral intention*, *trust* on abnormal *behavioral intention*

4.8 Testing Model

Table 8
Normality P Values results

Variable	P Values
<i>Behavioral intention</i> > <i>Use behavior</i>	0.209
<i>Effort expectancy</i> > <i>Behavioral intention</i>	0.000
<i>Facilitating Conditions</i> > <i>Behavioral intention</i>	0.001
<i>Facilitating Conditions</i> > <i>Use behavior</i>	0.000
<i>Perceived Risk</i> > <i>Behavioral intention</i>	0.229
<i>Performance expectancy</i> > <i>Behavioral intention</i>	0.000
<i>Social influence</i> > <i>Behavioral intention</i>	0.018
<i>Trust</i> > <i>Behavioral intention</i>	0.644

Based on data from table 8, showing data from P Values, the *behavioral intention* has no effect on *use behavior*, *effort expectancy* affects *behavioral intention*, *facilitating conditions* affect *behavioral intention*, *facilitating conditions* affect *use behavior*, the *perceived risk* does not affect *behavioral intention*, *performance expectancy* affects *behavioral intention*, *social influence* affects *behavioral intention*, *trust* does not affect *behavioral intention*

4.9 Hypothesis Testing

Figure 8 PLS Algorithm after bootstrapping

Figure 8 shows the results between variables above 0.65 which means that based on the value that can be *performance expectancy* affects *behavioral intention* and has a value of 4,576 because using the *cryptocurrency* transaction method in this *NFT* game can provide benefits to the public and the public will give good intentions to this transaction method *effort expectancy* affects *behavioral intention* and has a value of 3,534 because by using this transaction method, the public has no difficulty in operating it and can easily understand the transaction method, *social influence* affects *behavioral intention* and has a value of 2,511 because with the influence of *social influence*, it is hoped that influencers can provide education related to the *cryptocurrency* transaction method in this *NFT* game, *perceived risk* affects

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Behavioral intention and has a value of 1,180 because the public is already aware of the *risks* that exist in the use of *cryptocurrency* transaction methods in this *NFT* game, *trust* has no effect on *behavioral intentions* and has a value of 0.444 in this study, public *trust* is not a reference when using this *cryptocurrency* transaction method, facilitating conditions affect *behavioral intentions* and have a value of 3,071 because with the existence of facilities that support the community and the existence of a good transaction system and support the community, the community has more good intentions towards this transaction method, facilitating conditions affect *use behavior* and has a value of 14,235 in this study, good facilitating conditions will cause a sense of public desire to continue using this method This transaction, *behavioral intention* affects the *use behavior* and has a value of 1,189 with the effect of this variable, it will cause a sense of good intention of the community in adopting this transaction method and will cause a sense of wanting to use this transaction repeatedly.

V. CONCLUSION

Based on the results obtained from the research above, it can be concluded that all of the variables above are significantly interconnected and only 1 is not significantly related, namely between *trust* and *behavioral intention*. Based on the research conducted, the problem that occurs in this study is that they want to examine what factors cause people to want to make transactions in this *NFT* game and get the result that people feel that playing this *NFT* game can benefit them because they can carry out buying and selling activities using cryptocurrencies and for those who play this *NFT* game get additional benefits from the material and the public feels adopting this *NFT* game and using *cryptocurrency* as a transaction method can make it easier for them to carry out buying and selling activities.

The researcher's suggestion related to the results obtained above is that *cryptocurrency* should cooperate more with other games, not only with *NFT* games but must be able to invite other games to use *cryptocurrency* as a means of buying and selling transactions. Then the researcher also suggests doing routine system maintenance to avoid unwanted things and continue to invigorate to improve the quality of transaction methods. And in the results of the analysis, there is one variable that does not have a significant influence, namely *Trust* does not have a significant influence on *Use behavior*. This shows that there is no effect on public *trust* to adopt *cryptocurrency* transaction methods in this *NFT* game.

My advice in responding to this is to provide socialization related to this *cryptocurrency* transaction method to foster the *trust* of people who play games, especially games based on cryptocurrencies as a transaction method.

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